

the linear part of the fluorescence rise as indicated by the dashed line in Figure 1. Figure 1 also shows that both the rate of F_R and maximum fluorescence yield (F_{var}) declined after 8 d chilling at 10°C in the varieties Pungsan-byeo, Taebaeg-byeo, and Hanganchal-byeo.

Figure 2 compares the changes in chlorophyll fluorescence (as a percentage of the control at 27°C) after 8 d chilling at 10°C with the visual estimation of cold damage made on a 1 to 9 scale at the end of chilling. The japonica varieties Samnam-byeo (10) and Sangpung-byeo (11) were the most cold tolerant. Their fluorescence increased 23-34% during chilling. In contrast, indica/japonica varieties Taebaeg-byeo (1), Milyang 77 (9), Hanganchal-byeo (6), and Chupung-byeo (4) were the most susceptible to cold and F_R decreased 77, 89, 95, and 98% compared to the controls. The more cold-tolerant indica/japonica varieties tested had smaller decreases in chlorophyll fluorescence, which agreed with visual observations of injury (Fig. 2).

The increases in fluorescence of the more cold tolerant varieties Milyang 23 (7), Baegyung-byeo (8), Samnam-byeo (10), and Sangpung-byeo (11) after chilling are unusual and have not been reported. The increases can be interpreted as indicating acclimation or hardening to low temperatures and may be the result of increased chlorophyll content of the leaves at 10°C.

The agreement between changes in fluorescence and visual symptoms of cold injury indicates that chlorophyll fluorescence analysis could help plant breeders quickly screen large numbers of plants for cold tolerance. It is a sensitive, rapid, reproducible, nondestructive, and inexpensive technique.

Further evaluation of the chlorophyll fluorescence technique is needed in relation to plant development stage, sensitivity to other environmental factors, and different temperature treatments. The ability to detect cold damage to the thylakoid membranes by chlorophyll fluorescence analysis should not only be useful to plant breeders but also provide plant physiologists with insight into the causes and mechanisms of cold injury and hardening. □

1. Changes in the chlorophyll fluorescence kinetics of rice leaves of 3 varieties after 8 d chilling at 10°C, 85% relative humidity. The results are the mean measurements of 15 replications.

2. Changes in the rate of rise of variable fluorescence (F_R) of the leaves of 11 rice varieties (expressed as a percentage of the control at 27°C) after 8 d chilling at 10°C, 85% relative humidity compared with a visual assessment of injury on a 1 to 9 scale. 1) Taebaeg-byeo (I/J), 2) Chungchung-byeo (I/J), 3) Pungsan-byeo (I/J), 4) Chupung-byeo (I/J), 5) Milyang 23 (I/J), 6) Hanganchalbyeo (I/J), 7) Manseog-byeo (I/J), 8) Baeuang-byeo (I/J), 9) Milyang 77 (I/J), 10) Samnam-byeo (J), 11) Sangpung-byeo (J). I or J indicates whether variety is an indica or japonica or a cross between the 2.

A modified technique of screening for cold tolerance in rice

R. N. Kaw and G. S. Khush, IRRI

At IRRI, we measure cold tolerance by the degree of discoloration of 10-d-old

seedlings treated with 12°C water for 10 d. Although this screening method quickly discriminates between cultivars that remain green and those that turn yellow and die, it does not allow breeding materials to be ranked in relative order of hardiness, nor does it consider variations

Correlation coefficients between tolerance index and other attributes. IRRI, 1985.

Character	TI based on recovery 5 DAT	TI based on recovery 10 DAT	TI based on survival at second treatment	Recovery 5 DAT (% of resistant check)	Recovery 10 DAT (% of resistant check)	Survival on recovery 10 DAT (% of resistant check)	Cold tolerance score at first treatment
TI based on recovery 10 DAT	0.9960**						
TI based on survival at second treatment	0.7373**	0.7476**					
Recovery 5 DAT (% of resistant check)	0.8837**	0.8840**	0.6493**				
Recovery 10 DAT (% of resistant check)	0.8818**	0.8936**	0.6669**	0.9898**			
Survival on recovery 10 DAT (% of resistant check)	0.7305**	0.7404**	0.9474**	0.6753**	0.6898**		
Cold tolerance score at first treatment	-0.9677**	-0.9691**	-0.7117**	-0.8308**	-0.8410**	-0.7030**	
Cold tolerance score at second treatment	-0.8183**	-0.8283**	-0.9497**	-0.7275**	-0.7443**	-0.9427**	0.7865**

between tests. Cultivars rated tolerant (1-3) commonly vary in survival and recovery from cold. Survival or recovery is proportional to the condition of crop growth and inversely proportional to cold duration and intensity.

We screened 102 hybrids and their 23 parents for cold water tolerance at seedling stage. Objectives were to rank them by cold hardiness and to develop a way to quantify rice cold tolerance.

Twelve presprouted seeds, 1 row per culture, were grown in the greenhouse in porcelain trays for 10 d, then put in 12°C water tanks for 10 d. Every tray had 1 row each of susceptible IR8 and resistant Fujisaka 5. There were three replications. Plants per row were recorded before treatment. After 10 d, plants were scored, based on discoloration, by the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Plants were placed in the greenhouse and scored for recovery at 5 and 10 d after treatment (DAT) using a 0-1 scale (0 = dead, 0.5 = severely damaged but living, 1 = slight or no damage). The sum of scores on about 12 plants/test culture per replication was converted to a percentage of the average score of Fujisaka 5. Most F₁ hybrids recovered rapidly.

The test cultures underwent a second 10-d cold water treatment and were again rated for survival. Green seedlings had variable survival. It was difficult to discriminate cold tolerance of test cultures by leaf discoloration score alone and to rate them by cold hardiness as many cultures and Fujisaka 5 scored the same.

We developed a tolerance index (TI) to express leaf discoloration and survival/recovery percentage relative to the resistant check as a measure of cold tolerance:

$$TI = \frac{gi_2}{gi_1} \times \frac{100}{Ld_1} / \frac{C_2}{C_1} \times \frac{100}{Ld_2}$$

where gi₁ = number of plants before treatment,

gi₂ = number of plants after treatment,

Ld₁ = leaf discoloration score of the test culture,

Ld₂ = leaf discoloration score of the resistant check,

C₁ = number of plants in the resistant check before treatment, and

C₂ = number of resistant check plants that survived or recovered.

The formula can be rewritten as:

$$TI = \frac{gi_2 \times Ld_2 \times C_1}{gi_1 \times Ld_1 \times C_2}$$

Correlation coefficients between TI and other components and among the components are in the table. Associations between all attributes were highly significant. The highest correlation (0.996) was between TI at recovery 5 DAT and TI at recovery 10 DAT, followed by a strong association of cold tolerance score at first treatment with TI based on recovery at 10 DAT (-0.9691) and recovery 5 DAT (-0.9677). TI based on survival at second treatment was highly correlated with cold tolerance score at second treatment

(-0.9497) and with survival on recovery 10 DAT (0.9474).

We found that TI is a good indicator of cold tolerance stability, and concluded that one cold-water screening of seedlings based on TI would adequately rank the cultivars for cold tolerance.

Computation of TI values would eliminate variations between flats treated alike, and would also allow comparison between tests. The TI will equal unity if leaf discoloration scores and survival rates of the test cultivars and the resistant check are the same. A value > 1 will denote better cold tolerance than the check. TI data can be analyzed by analysis of variance and LSD. The TI may be appropriate for evaluating varieties and breeding lines for reaction to other stresses. □

Complete slide sets of photos printed in *Field problems of tropical rice*, revised 1983, are available for purchase at \$50 (less developed country price) or \$60 (developed country price), including airmail postage and handling, from the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. No orders for surface mail handling will be accepted.